

Binuclear complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base of salicylaldehyde and 1,2-propylenediamine with alkali metal salts of oxygen and nitrogen containing organic acids

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Abstract : A number of new heterobinuclear alkali metal complex of general formula $M_aPS.M_bL$ have been synthesized and characterized, where $M_a = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II} , PS = *N,N'*-1,2-propylene-bis(salicylaldimine), $M_b = \text{Li}$, Na or K and L = deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, electronic and IR spectral analysis, magnetic moment and molar conductance measurements. The IR spectra suggest bonding between the Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} metal chelate and alkali metal which appear by dative bond via oxygen atoms of C–O (phenolic). Low value of molar conductance would suggest them to be non-electrolyte. These complexes are biologically active against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *C. albicans* and so these may be treated as good antibacterial agents and fungicides. It was therefore, thought interesting to synthesize the title compounds and examine their antimicrobial activity.

Keywords : Heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes, antimicrobial studies, MIC.

Introduction

Schiff base posses strong ability to form metal complexes¹ and they deserve a proper attention because of their biological properties^{2,3}. The heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base are also biologically active⁴ and they exhibit enhanced activities as compared to their parent ligands.

We describe here the preparation and characterization of heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base. The Schiff's base was obtained by refluxing 1,2-propylenediamine and salicylaldehyde in 1 : 2 molar ratio respectively. The bonding between the *N,N'*-1,2-propylene-bis(salicylaldiminato)metal(II) complex (M_aPS) and the alkali metal is most likely to occur by dative bonding via the two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand which has been supported by infrared, electronic absorption spectra and magnetic properties studies of the adducts. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of the prepared complexes show the antimicrobial effectiveness.

Results and discussion

Both the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} metal chelate and their alkali metal adducts are coloured solids (Table 1) and stable at room temperature. The adducts are generally soluble in methanol, acetone, benzene and DMF, but insoluble in water. The lower melting/decomposition temperature of these adducts

than that of M_aPS , show the weak bonding through phenolic oxygen atoms to the alkali metals. Molar conductivities ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of complexes were measured in DMF at 30 (± 0.5) °C at the concentration of $10^{-3} M$. The compounds show low value (0.5–13.8 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of molar conductivity, indicating they are covalent in nature⁵ (Table 1). A value of about 35–40 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ appears characteristics of 1 : 1 electrolyte, where as ideally molar conductivity of a neutral complex should be zero⁶.

The infrared spectra of the CuPS, NiPS and their adducts (Table 2) exhibits band at the 1538–1570 cm^{-1} suggesting that this band may be due to the C–O stretching frequency⁷ in these compounds rather than C=N. Comparing C–O infrared bands for both the transition metal, we arrive at conclusion that the infrared bands for both transition metal complexes and alkali metal complexes remain almost same. The metal complex as ligand, exhibit the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic) at 1538 cm^{-1} , which shifts towards higher energy side on complex formation, indicating the coordination through the phenolic oxygen⁸. This shift is expected due to maintenance of a ring current arising from electron delocalisation in the chelating ring. The major shift of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic) to higher energy by $\sim 30 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in complexes is certainly indicating the presence of

Table 1. Analytical, magnetic and molar conductance data of the complexes

Compd. [M _a PS.M _b L]	Colour	Melt.(m)/dec.(d)/ dec.(d)/trans.(t) temp. (°C)	Molar cond.	μ _{eff}	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Yield (%)
					C	H	N	M _a	M _b	
CuPS	Purple	255d	-	-	58.91 (59.39)	4.42 (4.66)	7.68 (8.15)	18.21 (18.49)	-	74.62
CuPS.LiONP	Golden brown	228m	1.4	1.84	56.46 (56.50)	4.01 (4.09)	8.52 (8.60)	12.88 (13.00)	1.37 (1.43)	77.79
CuPS.NaONP	Purple	247m	0.5	-	54.62 (54.71)	3.87 (3.96)	8.22 (8.33)	12.53 (12.59)	4.41 (4.56)	72.84
CuPS.KONP	Purple	245m	0.6	-	52.82 (53.03)	3.72 (3.84)	7.88 (8.07)	12.12 (12.20)	7.41 (7.49)	66.76
CuPS.LiDNP	Brownish red	245m	3.2	1.74	51.55 (51.73)	3.47 (3.56)	10.45 (10.50)	11.83 (11.90)	1.21 (1.31)	73.10
CuPS.NaDNP	Brownish yellow	202m	3.3	-	50.18 (50.23)	3.35 (3.46)	10.13 (10.19)	11.49 (11.56)	4.14 (4.19)	75.07
CuPS.KDNP	Teak brown	241m	6.1	-	48.77 (48.81)	3.22 (3.36)	9.81 (9.90)	11.14 (11.23)	6.78 (6.90)	76.04
CuPS.LiTNP	Brownish yellow	218m	6.5	-	47.52 (47.71)	3.02 (3.11)	12.02 (12.10)	10.79 (10.98)	1.11 (1.21)	76.92
CuPS.NaTNP	Brownish yellow	266m	7.2	1.73	46.31 (46.43)	2.88 (3.03)	11.62 (11.77)	10.55 (10.68)	3.73 (3.87)	70.65
CuPS.KTNP	Brownish yellow	278m	8.9	-	45.05 (45.21)	2.82 (2.95)	11.41 (11.47)	10.28 (10.40)	6.31 (6.39)	66.75
CuPS.Li1N2N	Brown	228m	0.7	-	61.83 (62.01)	4.03 (4.21)	7.95 (8.04)	12.05 (12.15)	1.30 (1.34)	78.95
CuPS.Na1N2N	Leaf brown	226m	2.0	-	60.10 (60.17)	3.91 (4.09)	7.67 (7.80)	11.68 (11.79)	4.18 (4.27)	70.57
CuPS.K1N2N	Brown	225m	2.4	1.94	58.38 (58.43)	3.82 (3.97)	7.48 (7.57)	11.31 (11.45)	6.88 (7.03)	74.39
NiPS	Brownish orange	282m	-	-	59.97 (60.23)	4.63 (4.72)	8.11 (8.27)	16.98 (17.33)	-	79.28
NiPS.LiONP	Deep orange	271m	12.2	-	56.95 (57.06)	3.99 (4.13)	8.50 (8.63)	12.01 (12.14)	1.32 (1.45)	77.01
NiPS.NaONP	Brownish yellow	278m	4.1	-	55.15 (55.23)	3.88 (4.00)	8.31 (8.41)	11.41 (11.47)	4.48 (4.60)	72.54
NiPS.KONP	Brick red	282m	3.7	-	53.40 (53.52)	3.79 (3.88)	8.11 (8.14)	11.31 (11.38)	7.48 (7.56)	75.63
NiPS.LiDNP	Brick red	110m	12.0	-	52.11 (52.20)	3.45 (3.59)	10.45 (10.59)	11.02 (11.10)	1.27 (1.32)	73.77
NiPS.NaDNP	Brownish yellow	226m	13.8	-	50.55 (50.67)	3.42 (3.49)	10.15 (10.28)	10.63 (10.78)	4.11 (4.22)	76.65
NiPS.KDNP	Brownish orange	282m	4.1	-	49.05 (49.22)	3.29 (3.39)	9.89 (9.99)	10.40 (10.47)	6.86 (6.96)	78.03
NiPS.LiTNP	Lemon yellow	238m	7.3	-	48.02 (48.11)	3.01 (3.14)	12.11 (12.20)	12.15 (12.23)	1.12 (1.22)	82.36
NiPS.NaTNP	Brownish orange	290t	3.1	-	46.65 (46.80)	2.98 (3.08)	11.82 (11.87)	9.89 (9.95)	3.80 (3.90)	85.64
NiPS.KTNP	Golden yellow	260d	6.4	-	45.45 (45.57)	2.90 (2.97)	11.51 (11.56)	9.62 (9.69)	6.41 (6.44)	80.49
NiPS.Li1N2N	Brownish yellow	278m	3.7	-	62.42 (62.58)	4.11 (4.25)	7.98 (8.11)	11.22 (11.34)	1.26 (1.35)	81.61
NiPS.Na1N2N	Brownish yellow	265t	11.9	-	60.65 (60.71)	4.02 (4.12)	7.75 (7.87)	10.88 (11.00)	4.18 (4.31)	81.97
NiPS.K1N2N	Teak brown	280t	10.7	-	58.79 (58.94)	3.88 (4.00)	7.55 (7.64)	10.55 (10.58)	6.91 (7.09)	78.68

where, ONP = 2-nitrophenol, DNP = 2,4-dinitrophenol, TNP = 2,4,6-trinitrophenol and 1N2N = 1-nitroso-2-naphthol; m – sharp melting point, d – decomposition temperature, md – melting with decomposition and t – transition temperature.

Table 2. Spectral data of metal chelate and their metal complexes

Compd.	Infrared spectra (cm ⁻¹)			Electronic spectra Diffuse reflectance (in nm)
	v(C-O) phenolic	v(M-N)	v(M-O)	
CuPS	1538	505	466	219, 242, 263, 352, 652
CuPS.LiONP	1570	-	-	226, 267, 351, 652
CuPS.LiDNP	1550	548	469	224, 266, 352, 653
CuPS.NaTNP	1568	541, 515	461	224, 266, 351, 652
CuPS.KIN2N	1565	516	470	225, 267, 353, 652
NiPS	1538	552	488, 463	239, 316, 395, 653
NiPS.LiONP	1550	555	463	207, 239, 324, 393, 652
NiPS.LiDNP	1560	540	466	239, 326, 394, 653
NiPS.NaTNP	1567	545	490	207, 237, 345, 653
NiPS.KIN2N	1565	546	462	219, 255, 377, 652

phenoxobridge. It is, therefore, suggestive that the phenol C-O link attained a considerable amount of partial double bond character in these complexes. This is what to be expected from the readiness with which these binuclear complexes were formed.

In all the present complexes, the bands with medium to strong absorption in the far IR region 515–555 cm⁻¹ and 463–490 cm⁻¹ tentatively assigned to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} modes respectively. These bands are not present in the Schiff base of 1,2-propylenediamine and salicylaldehyde, while in neutral transition metal chelates (CuPS and NiPS) at the region 505–502 cm⁻¹ and 463–488 cm⁻¹. These assignments are based on the assumption⁹ that since oxygen atom is more electronegative than nitrogen atom, the M-O band tends to be more ionic than the M-N bond. Consequently, M-O vibrations are expected to appear at lower frequency. The above data confirm the coordination of oxygen atom of phenolic group and nitrogen atom of -NO, -NO₂ etc. to alkali metal in all the binuclear complexes.

The electronic absorption bands (Table 2) for the chelate neutral complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{III} metals of ligand (CuPS and NiPS) is observed between 219–316 nm indicating the formation of $\pi-\pi^*$ transition in aromatic ring and C=N chromophore. The bands appearing between 352–650 nm in Cu^{II} and Ni^{III} complexes (i.e. CuPS and NiPS) shows that there is d-d transition and charge transfer^{10,11}.

The electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes may arise due to the following transitions : (i) d-d transition, (ii) charge transfer transition and (iii) internal ligand transition.

The spectra of all copper(II) bridge complexes also gave similar type of bands around 352 nm and 625 nm. This suggests that there is no changes in stereochemistry of the complexes after adduct formation. This is supported by the magnetic values of the adducts too. The electronic absorption bands located around ~652 nm along with a medium shoulder around ~352 nm may be attributed to arise due to d-d transition. However, the possibility of charge transfer for the peak ~400 nm may not be completely ruled out and other bands appear between 224–267 nm due to internal ligand transition.

The absorption band of medium intensity in NiPS at 395 nm in electronics spectra suggests the square planar structure of Ni²⁺ with the coordination number 4 as well as it is red colour. The absorption band of binuclear alkali metal complexes derived from NiPS is found in the range of 345 nm to 653 nm suggesting the same square planar geometry of NiPS with coordination number 4 in all the alkali metal adducts. As the coordination of Ni²⁺ in NiPS remains same in adducts, it is clear that alkali metal salts are not attached through Ni²⁺. No absorption bands have been found in the range of 700 nm to 1200 nm in the binuclear alkali metal complexes. Had it been six coordinated complex of Ni^{II}, the absorption bands must have been obtained in the range of 700 nm to 1200 nm for octahedral or tetrahedral Ni^{II} complex. The absence of these bands in electronic spectra further confirms that the coordination number of Ni²⁺ in NiPS binuclear alkali metal complex compounds have not been raised but it remains four (4) with square planar structure.

Table 3. MIC values of some of the adducts of M₂PS with alkali metal salts of organic acids

Compd.	Concn.	Percentage inhibition		
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
NiPS.LiTNP	200	100	100	100
	100	100	100	100
	50	100	85-90	100
	25	85-90	85-90	85-90
NiPS.LiIN2N	200	85-90	50-55	85-90
	100	85-90	50-55	85-90
	50	85-90	50-55	85-90
	25	50-55	50-55	50-55
CuPS.LiDNP	200	100	85-90	85-90
	100	85-90	85-90	85-90
	50	85-90	50-55	50-55
	25	50-55	50-55	50-55
CuPS.KIN2N	200	100	100	100
	100	100	100	100
	50	85-90	85-90	100
	25	85-90	85-90	85-90

The magnetic moment value of CuPS and its adduct lies between 1.73 to 1.94 B.M., which correspond to the presence of one unpaired electron and the square planar geometry with coordination number 4. Very low value (approximately zero) of magnetic moment of NiPS and its adducts is observed which suggests the diamagnetic behaviour and square planar geometry with coordination number 4.

Antimicrobial activity :

The heterobinuclear complexes were tested for their antibacterial activity against bacteria viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and fungus viz. *Candida albicans* by serial dilution method in DMF in the concentration range 25–200 µg ml⁻¹. The MIC results of some of the complexes are shown in Table 3.

From above results we summarised that most of the adducts of NiPS and CuPS shows great degree of activity at higher concentration against test organism (bacteria *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and fungi *Candida albicans* and also as the concentration of these adducts increases the antimicrobial activity also increase gradually.

Experimental

Synthetic procedures :

A.R. grade reagents have been used for synthesizing all the compounds. IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer, Shimadzu model-8201 PC in KBr phase. Electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 15 UVB VIS spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurement was performed on Gouy balance.

The Schiff base on salicylaldehyde and 1,2-propylenediamine were prepared by the refluxing the aldehyde and diamine in 2 : 1 molar proportion in ethanol for 10 min. The yellow Schiff base was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried in oven. A solution of copper(II) acetate hydrate (2.0 g) or nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (2.5 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was added slowly with stirring to a hot solution of the Schiff base (PS, 2.82 g). The solution upon cooling deposited purple copper complex or the brownish-orange nickel complex. These were filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried in electric oven.

Heterobinuclear complexes containing Cu^{II} metal and alkali metal : *N,N'*-1,2-Propylene-bis(salicylideneiminato) copper(II) [CuPS] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, dinitrophenol, trinitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol were added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75–80 °C with stirring for 1–1½ h. The characteristic colour adducts were precipitated in hot condition, which was filtered, washed with absolute ethanol, dried in electric oven at 80 °C and finally kept in desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Heterobinuclear complexes containing Ni^{II} metal and alkali metal : *N,N'*-1,2-Propylene-bis(salicylideneiminato) nickel(II) [NiPS] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, dinitrophenol, trinitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol were added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75–80 °C with stirring for 1–1½ h. The characteristic colour adducts were precipitated in hot

condition, which was filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol, dried in electric oven at 80 °C and finally kept in desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Conclusion :

The bonding between the *N,N'*-1,2-propylene-bis(salicylideneiminato)metal(II) complex (M_aPS) and the alkali metal is most likely to occur by dative bonding via the two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand which has been supported by the IR spectra, magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of the adducts. The stoichiometry and the physico-chemical studies as discussed above suggests square planar geometry of M_bPS (where M_b = Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}) with coordination number 4 in all its alkali metal adducts. The probable structure and bonding of the newly prepared compounds with general formula [M_aPS.M_bL] may be shown as in Fig. 1.

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Fig. 1. Probable structure and bonding of complex.

where M_aPS = CuPS or NiPS; M_b = Li, Na or K; $\begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ \text{L} \\ \text{O or N} \end{matrix}$ = alkali metal salts of 2-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol.